

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL MASTERY OF THE LEVEL OF SPEECH COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS AS A DIDACTIC BASIS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the consideration of theoretical and practical mastery of the level of speech competence of future teachers as a basic part of the didactic basis, the preparation of speech competence with the ability to written and oral communication. The article examines the content-structural essence of speech competence, its significance. Attention is focused on the degree of mastery of speech competence reflects the professional and personal level of development of future teachers, and competence itself occupies a special place among the components of linguistic education, the problem of formation of mastery of the level of speech training of future teachers is touched upon, the question of the didactic basis is considered, the system of tasks aimed at mastering speech training and increasing the level of speech competence is analyzed.*

Keywords: *speech competence; competence approach; speech culture; cognitive activity; task system, didactic basis.*

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ РЕЧЕВОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ КАК ДИДАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ОСНОВА

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена рассмотрению теоретического и практического овладения уровнем речевой компетенции будущих учителей как базовой части дидактической основы подготовки речевой компетенции с умением к письменной и устной коммуникации. В статье рассматривается содержательно-структурная сущность речевой компетенции, ее значение. Акцентируется внимание на том, что степень овладения речевой компетенцией отражает профессионально-личностный уровень развития будущих педагогов, а сама компетентность занимает особое место среди компонентов лингвистического образования, проблема формирования овладения уровнем речевой подготовки учащихся. будущих учителей, затронут вопрос о дидактической основе, проанализирована система заданий, направленных на овладение речевой подготовкой и повышение уровня речевой компетенции.*

Ключевые слова: *речевая компетентность; компетентностный подход; культура речи; познавательная деятельность; система заданий, дидактическая основа.*

Theoretical and practical mastery of the level of speech competence of future teachers as a didactic basis

Currently, much attention is paid to speech competence in the preparation of future teachers. Future teachers should not only be educated, capable of analyzing and solving complex problem situations, but also should pay attention to their own speech culture, which is an obligatory component of their professional and personal development. The level of speech competence is an indicator of the state of the general culture of future teachers. Today, our republic needs competent specialists who are suitable for professional growth, therefore, the level of proficiency in speech competence is an indicator of professionalism. The discipline "Culture of speech" has been introduced in Higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, upon completion of training, future teachers should be able to demonstrate their knowledge and skills in the use of all speech norms. The culture of speech is speech constructed

in accordance with the norms of the modern language, in this case, the modern Russian literary language. To observe the norms of the modern language means to know the rules and traditions of the use of language units in the field of phonetics and orthoepy, vocabulary, grammar, spelling and punctuation, stylistics and in accordance with this to build their statements. Speech should be not only normative, but also communicative and meaningful, that is, it should be distinguished by correctness, relevance and richness. Literary language is the common language of the written language of the people, science, journalism, fiction, all manifestations of culture expressed in verbal form. This language is considered exemplary. Recently, future teachers are faced with the fact that most of them do not read well, they do not know how to express their thoughts both orally and in writing. This does not mean that they do not speak or write, in other words, their speech communication skills are at a low level of development. There are various methodological recommendations for the organization of work on the formation of the speech competence of future teachers. First, attention should be paid to reading texts of different styles and genres. In your work, you need to use different types of reading: studying, introductory, viewing. When reading, it is necessary to practice intonation skills that form the expressiveness of speech. So, for example, you can offer to listen to texts read by the best actors in an audio recording, and then the students themselves can practice expressive reading. Secondly, at each lesson, the teacher must conduct vocabulary work, during which not only the lexical meanings of the word are fixed, but also its spelling, pronunciation, use with other words in the sentence. Thirdly, it is important to train future teachers to navigate in the speech space, to understand which words, phrases, expressions, grammatical constructions are characteristic of a particular situation.

Speech competence is conditioned by language competence, wide speech practice of communication, a large volume of reading and literature of different genres and determines communicative competence. It includes motivational-target, meaningful and personal components and performs the following functions: cognitive, informative, communicative, stimulating. The necessity of forming the speech competence of future teachers is justified because it determines, on the one hand, personal development, and, on the other, the level of development of society as a whole. Speech is a structure-forming element of education, since it is knowledge of the language that makes it possible to fully master academic disciplines. The phenomenality of speech competence determines the dynamics of its interdisciplinary nature. The concept of speech competence was introduced and justified by L.S. Vygotsky and developed by his students (P.Ya. Galperin, T. Leontieva, etc.). L.S. Vygotsky believed that speech should be considered as a means of communication, utterance and understanding. In the works of L.V. Kazantseva, speech competence refers to the knowledge, skills, skills and powers of a teacher to designate the optimal solution to the problems of a foreign language lesson. For example, S.N. Mitina, investigating the problem of the formation of the speech competence of future teachers, includes in the analyzed concept, in addition to communicative skills, also knowledge of the basic concepts of linguistics. According to T.V., Shmeleva, speech competence indicates the level of proficiency in the basic skills and abilities of all types of speech activity in the spheres and genres of communication vital for a particular age and can be presented in the context of parameters: roles where the author, generating a statement, performs a receptive role, and the addressee, perceiving the author, plays a creative role. Speech competence is the result of a person mastering speech activity. This competence is manifested in speech activity as the basis of human activity. The specificity of speech competence is due to the fact that it is fundamental in both the personal and professional components of future teachers. The specifics of the work of

future teachers determines the special requirements for his speech activity and in the educational process. The uniqueness of speech competence lies in the fact that it is the result of the educational process and a means of education. Being a special independent type of activity, speech competence is a necessary part of any activity performed together with other people. The essence of the profession of future teachers lies in their interaction with students in the pedagogical process. The educational process is realized in speech activity through communication and cognition, therefore future teachers should understand and realize the importance of speech activity. Speech competence permeates the entire educational process because:

- is a means of learning future teachers;
- is an expression of the cognitive activity of future teachers ;
- is the basis of various interpersonal relationships;
- contributes to the formation of future teachers as a subject of professional activity, and hence their competence.

The specificity of competence-based training of future teachers consists in mastering their methods of action, mastering new technologies that allow them to perform non-algorithmic (new for them) actions in conditions of atypical ways of expressing the theory and practice of the development of future teachers' speech competencies, the presence of competing components, the presence of syncretism phenomena. The educational process organized on the basis of competence-based learning contributes to the formation of an activity-based approach to mastering speech concepts. However, there are contradictions between the traditional approach to the organization of the educational process for the study of speech concepts and competence, the characteristics of which are the integration of the process of mastering a certain amount of knowledge and skills and mastering technologies, the theoretical assessment of language units when they are considered by future teachers from the side of their properties, identifying their distinctive features and applying the acquired knowledge to the analysis of non-standard cases manifestations of linguistic units. The resolution of this contradiction should be facilitated by the system of formation of the speech competence of future teachers, based on the ideas of a competence-based approach to learning.

A competence-based approach to learning requires future teachers to master a certain set of ways of working with speech phenomena. The knowledge they acquire in the learning process should be focused on their independent use in the learning process, even in changing conditions. The formation of knowledge is connected with the rational correlation of the process of mastering the necessary knowledge and the process of mastering the methods of their assimilation, which ensures the unity of the study of grammatical theory and the development of cognitive powers of future teachers, their ability to independently, creatively use knowledge in the practice of language analysis and speech creativity (the formation of speech competence), the technology of theoretical evaluation of language units when they are considered future teachers from the side of the complex of their properties, identification of their distinctive features and application of acquired knowledge to the analysis of non-standard cases of manifestation of linguistic units. A competence-based approach to learning requires future teachers to master a certain set of ways of working with language phenomena. The knowledge acquired in the learning process should be focused on their independent use in the learning process, even in changing conditions. The competence approach to teaching the Russian language allows us to identify the level of language proficiency of the learner, which is an indicator of the development of a speech personality (the level of special knowledge, knowledge of ways of dealing with

language material and the ability to use acquired knowledge in non-standard situations), namely: the use of speech in teaching as a multifunctional phenomenon: a means of communication, a tool of cognition and reflection reality, a means of intellectual and spiritual development of the individual; achievements of modern psychological and linguistic science in the theory of speech activity.

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